

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

МОДУЛИРОВАННЫЙ МАТЕРИАЛ ДЛЯ САМОСТОЯТЕЛЬНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

Пиримжаров М.Х.,

к.п.н., доцент

Казахско-русский международный университета,

г. Актобе, Республики Казахстан

Тилеужанова Р.А.

Магистр

Актюбинский региональный университет им. К. Жубанова

г. Актобе, Республики Казахстан

Тайманова З.Б.

Магистр

Актюбинский региональный университет им. К. Жубанова

г. Актобе, Республики Казахстан

MODULATED MATERIAL FOR INDEPENDENT EDUCATION

Pirimjarov M.,

Ph.D., Associate Professor

Kazakh-Russian International University,

Aktobe, Republic of Kazakhstan

Tileuzhanova R.,

Magistr

Aktobe Regional University named after K. Zhubanov

Taimanova Z.

Magistr

Aktobe Regional University named after K. Zhubanov

Аннотация

В процессе самостоятельного образования обучаемый вправе выбирать содержание образования. Оно отражает цели и задачи обучаемого в усвоении определенных знаний и умений.

Это - разработка научно - методических материалы самостоятельного образования располагает различными дидактическими возможностями, а именно:

- повышает (закрепляет) знания, умения и навыки обучаемого;
- активизирует основные идеи, понятия, процессы, связанные с изучаемыми процессами;
- передает изучаемый материал;
- расширяет объем знаний обучаемого;
- формирует практические навыки и умения обучаемого;
- управляет деятельностью преподавателя по обучению и познавательную деятельность обучаемого;
- стимулирует научный подход к созданию нового материала для самостоятельного образования [1, С. 5].

Abstract

In the process of independent education, the student has the right to choose the content of education. It reflects the goals and objectives of the learner in mastering certain knowledge and skills.

This is the development of scientific and methodological materials for independent education has various didactic possibilities, namely:

- increases (strengthens) the knowledge, skills and abilities of the student;
- activates the main ideas, concepts, processes related to the processes being studied;
- transmits the studied material;
- expands the amount of knowledge of the student;
- forms the practical skills and abilities of the student;
- manages the teacher's learning activities and the cognitive activity of the student;
- stimulates a scientific approach to the creation of new material for independent education [1, p. 5].

Ключевые слова: дидактика, интеллектуальное, мотивация, инновация, классификация, дифференция, интеграция, динамизм, материал, задача, уровень, модуль, критерия, процесс.

Keywords: didactics, intellectual, motivation, innovation, classification, differentiation, integration, dynamism, material, task, level, module, criteria, process.

INTRODUCTION

The materials of independent education used in the system of independent education assume various tasks. Among them we can list informational, cognitive, educational, intellectual, developmental, self-determination, management, motivational, control, stimulating, innovative and other tasks.

The materials of independent education are classified according to several criteria [2. p. 117;119]:

1. By the nature of the educational material: knowledge and information obtained from textbooks, educational and methodological manuals; additional material; standard texts of lectures, etc.

2. According to the volume of educational information: the full volume of the studied questions, information on the subject of the discipline. Information technology-related material.

3. By the term of use: handout for one-time use. Material used in the classroom more than once.

The material of independent education, communication between students and the teacher are the leading components in the process of independent education. The degree of interaction of these two components contributes to the equation of models of open education [3, p. 1;56].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This activity will be effective under the following circumstances. The student's activity will be effective if he can independently use educational and training materials, distinguish and analyze them. At the same time, the following skills of the trainee are important:

- work with scientific documentation, highlighting the uniqueness in its content, classification of the studied phenomena and factors;

- analysis of the educational material, highlighting the leading ideas and their argumentation (justification);

- systematization of educational material, identification of the main components, determination of pronounced connections between them and their didactic capabilities;

- regulation (ordering) of the process of using the material of independent education, their replenishment and updating [4. p. 5].

It should be taken into account the fact that many students have not previously faced the problem of independent work with the material of independent education. The materials of independent education, unlike textbooks, educational and methodological manuals, are complex by the nature of the structure. As practice shows, many trainees in the learning process cannot objectively assess their skills in working with material for independent education. This assessment is always personal (subjective). A serious problem arises – how to ensure the objectivity of this process. In our opinion, there is a solution to this problem – it is necessary to develop, define, justify and apply criteria for assessing students' skills with material for independent education. Certain criteria should be dynamic and flexible. Each student chooses criteria in accordance with readiness for self-assessment, organization and correction of their activities [5. p. 30].

The criteria for assessing the level of mastery of students' skills of independent work with the material of independent education look like this:

- the highest level – the student has assimilated the educational information transmitted during lectures and practical classes on the subject, is inclined to consolidate and expand the scope of this information. He is familiar with the electronic textbook and other literature available in the center of information and resources of the educational institution, has the skills to draw the necessary material from them and perform independent work correctly and in full;

- high level – the student has mastered the educational information transmitted in lectures and practical classes on the subject, but is indifferent to the consolidation and expansion of this information, is familiar with the literature available in the information and resources center of the educational institution, sometimes devotes time to this;

- intermediate level - the student partially possesses the skills of independent work with the material for independent education, i.e. is not familiar with electronic literature available in the center of information and resources of an educational institution, audio, video materials, materials, partially possesses the knowledge and skills to perform independent work [6. p.127].

The material for independent education is the main link of independent education. Their completeness and practicality largely determines the effectiveness of the educational process. In these conditions, it is important to enrich the material for independent education on an ongoing basis.

The first link in the chain of cognition of any subject or phenomenon, including educational material, is the perception of the material being studied. The student perceives the material on descriptive geometry mainly through visual and auditory analyzers, since the student simultaneously explains the theoretical state, demonstrates its spatial scheme, and graphical actions for practical implementation in projections, i.e. in conventionally flat images. At the same time, the students' minds reflect mainly the current properties and signs of the phenomena being explained. With the development of the topic, the content and related graphic images are mutually replaced [7. p. 335].

Now traces of the perceived phenomenon remain in the student's mind, i.e. separate ideas about the properties and signs of the material being explained. For example, the position of a point in space is explained in connection with the nature of its location on octants. But the representation of the point projections in relation to the projection axis remains in the students' minds, and the student tries to remember them. This is both the perception of the material of the topic being studied and the primary awareness, in it the scientific understanding of the true essence, causes and effects is carried out with the help of thinking, since it is impossible to achieve this only with feelings. The more representations in the student's mind were formed with the help of perception, the more accurate and transparent they are, the more material for thinking. It is perceived by auditory analyzers, since the teacher, explaining the theoretical position, simultaneously connects it with the

spatial scheme, the understanding of the material in projections, its spatial imagination. The student must have an irritated imagination that provides a complete representation of geometric formations occurring in space, not to lose sight of any part of them [8. p.18;31].

By repeated actions of the student by applying knowledge in practice, his knowledge is deepened, skills and abilities are formed, creative abilities and talent are developed. In each regular exercise, the student discovers new facets of the material being studied and realizes it more deeply. The importance of independent education in solving these problems is important, its proper organization and the right choice of material [9. p.17;23].

The level of complexity and difficulty of independent work should have the character of growth and development, thereby ensuring different thinking and mental independence of the student. Independent work should combine the setting of creative tasks and creative activity through analysis in exercises (1-figure). For example, it is required to determine from a given horizontal and frontal projection of point A in which quarter of space it is located [10. .319].

1-drawing

The problem is solved in the following logical way:

1. The point can be located in any quarter of space, i.e. A (1,2,3,4).

2. The frontal projection of point A can be below the projection axis x, i.e. A (3,4).

3. The horizontal projection of point A1 is located above the x axis, which means that according to the movement of the plane of horizontal projections H around the x axis, it is located in the 3rd quarter, i.e. A(3).

Following such a reflection, the student can easily solve such problems.

Now we will place the front projection A2 in the x axis. in the following example, place A1 in the x-axis. This state of affairs requires a creative approach from the student. In the previous examples, the distance of the point from the projection plane did not matter much, it was not even remembered. In the new examples (tasks), the issue of the remoteness of a point from the projection planes comes to the fore and becomes relevant. By solving new problems, the student determines the position of a point in a part of the projection plane. The total number of such positions is 26, the student receives ample opportunities for the formation of skills and abilities. Taking into account the tasks assigned to independent education, the topics should be chosen as follows:

1. Tasks similar to the problems proved during practical classes, or such tasks, the way of solving which is similar to the previously shown.

2. The introduction of individual theoretical knowledge into practice.

3. Announcement of the main information on the topic, their generalization and formulation of conclusions.

4. Additional topics that are a continuation of what has been passed, but easy to understand.

5. Topics designed to expand what has been passed.

6. Tasks that require a creative approach.

Below is a diagram of a modular system for preparing independent education material.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The module is a relatively small part of the material of independent education, which consists of the presentation of some interrelated ideas, proofs, phenomena. Most often it is educational, methodological and managerial information. The trainee can study them in a short time. This is due to the possibility of concentration of attention in the intensive process of cognition.

The modules are related to a number of factors: intended educational material, quantitative characteristics of the contingent, the purpose of training, form, method and content. They can be multiplied or decreased due to these factors. Usually, modules are combined according to the individual sections of the training course.

Structural components (components) of the module:

1. Instructions, ways of independent education, goals and objectives of the educational material.

2. The content of the educational material to be assimilated by the trainees.

3. Independent tasks, practical tasks to consolidate the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities.

4. Criteria for self-assessment by trainees in order to verify the results of independent education.

5. Methodological material that ensures the quality of independent teaching (manuals, instructions, recommendations).

6. Sources of educational and methodological information used in the process of independent learning.

The main characteristics of the module:

- independence – the module as a structural unit has a private content of education that differs from others;

- limited time to implement the goals and objectives of the module;

- dynamism – the ability to quickly change the component of the module in accordance with the goals and objectives of independent education;

- components of the module–differentiation and integration of structural components. Their performance of a kind of practical task;

- interdependence and interrelation of the components of the module: each of which is interconnected by location in the structure of the module;

- the effectiveness of studying independent educational material due to its relatively smaller volume;

- the ability to evaluate the learner's cognitive activity;

- integrity, the need to use a set of structural components that reflect the functions of the module;
- the module can be presented in any form: printed, audio recordings, computer programs, etc.[11. p. 93].

CONCLUSION

The material of independent education developed on the basis of a modular system differs from the traditional educational material, first of all, by the presence of didactic and methodological components that indicate to the educational process managers and trainees methodological methods and effective forms of independent cognition.

Thus, the modulated material for independent education is considered as an important factor in the process of management, control and correction of the student's independent education.

References

1. Pirimjarov M.Kh., abstract of the dissertation "Improving the graphic training of future architects in the system of higher education" (PhD degree), - T.: 2009., [1, p. 5].
2. Zoirov K.A., Theoretical foundations of the intensification of graphic training of future engineer-teacher in the system higher professional education. / J. Ta'lim muammolari, - T.: 2003., №2-4., [2. p. 117;119].
3. Slastenin V.A., On modeling educational technologies., / J. Science and School, - 2000. - №4, [3. p. 1;56].
4. Derazhne Yu., System of educational technologies, / J. Science and school, 2001., №3, [4. p. 5]
5. Arkhangelsk S.I., Some new tasks of higher education and requirements for pedagogical skills, - M.: Znanie., 1986., [5. p. 30].
6. Farberman B.L., New pedagogical technologies, - T.: UzAN "FAN", 2000., [6. p.127].
7. Bepalko V.P., Pedagogy and progressive learning technologies, -M.: Enlightenment, 1997., [7. p. 335].
8. Bogolyubov V.I., Methods and means of implementing pedagogical technologies. / Zh. School technologies, -M.: 2004., №4., [8. p.18;31].
9. Bushlya A.K., About self-education / J. Pedagogy. 1989., No. 2, [9. p.17;23].
10. Koroev Yu.I., Descriptive geometry, Specialty "Architecture". - M.: Stroyizdat, 1987., [10. p.319].
11. Gilford J. Structural components of the module. 2004. [11. p. 93].